

Effect of the Phenological Stage on the Antioxidant and Antimicrobial Activity of Artemisia Herba-Alba and Artemisia Campestris Essential Oils

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Abstract: *The essential oils obtained by hydrodistillation from the aerial parts of two endemic species of Artemisia (Asteraceae) collected from the Center of Tunisia (Maknessi), was analysed by GC-MS. Twelve to fourteen components were identified representing more than 80% of the total oil. The essential oil composition and yield showed a variation related to the harvest period. The yield of the essential oils of A. campestris harvested on December was 0.44 % and the one of May was 0.30 %. For A. herba-alba it was 0.5 % for air dried leaves harvested on December and 0.8 % for the one of May. It is observed that the major component in the essential oils for both species is α -thujone followed by cis-sabinol and β -thujone for the extract of December. However, the major compound is β -pinene followed by p-cymen for Artemisia campestris extract of May. The major component of A. campestris α -thujone was absent in the essential oil of the seed stage. This variability could be explained by the phenological stage of the plant. The essential oils of two Artemisia species showed significant antifungal activity against a weak antimicrobial activity.*

Keywords: *Artemisia campestris; Artemisia herba-alba; essential oil composition; antimicrobial activity.*

Introduction

Artemisia is a large, diverse genus of plants with almost 400 species belonging to the Asteracea family. Most of Artemisia species grow in temperate climates, usually in dry or semi-dry habitats. Artemisia comprises hardy herbaceous plants and shrubs, which are known for many chemical constituents in their essential oils. Many species are known by their volatile oil and are applied in therapy because of their high content in pharmacologically active compounds. Many of the plant components that are so vital to the survival and reproduction of the plants, leaves, flowers, volatile oils, also provide a larger value for humans. The leaves and essential oils are used medicinally, including the production of an anti-malarial compound from A. annua. Various species are used for culinary purposes, with A. absinthium used in vermouth and absinthe, and A. dracunculus (tarragon) popular in French cuisine. Although many species are wind-pollinated, there is evidence of insect pollination for some species (Tkach et al., 2007), with the flowers offering nectar to the insects in exchange for pollination. The attractive foliage and colourful flower-heads of some species make them desirable ornamental plants. The aromatic leaves of many species of Artemisia are medicinal, and some are used for flavouring. Most species have an extremely bitter taste. Artemisia oils had inhibitory effects on the growth of bacteria (Escherichia coli, Staphylococcus aureus and Staphylococcus epidermidis), yeasts (Candida albicans, Cryptococcus neoformans) and dermatophytes (Trichophyton rubrum, Microsporum canis and Microsporum gypseum), Fonsecaea pedrosoi and Aspergillus nige (Lopes-Lutz et al., 2008).

Essential oil of the aerial parts of A. herba-alba has been studied extensively and large chemical variability has been reported. Two types of oils can be distinguished: those whose composition is dominated by a major compound and those characterized by the occurrence of two or more main compounds in an appreciable concentration. Many studies have shown antidiabetic, antimicrobial, antifungic, leishmanicidal, anti-oxidant, and spasmolytic properties of A. herba-alba extracts and essential oils (Yashphe et al., 1979; Hatimi et al., 2001; Tahraoui et al., 2007).

A. campestris is widespread in the south of Tunisia. The leaves of this plant are widely used in

traditional medicine as a decoction for their antivenom, anti-inflammatory, antirheumatic and antimicrobial activities (Le Floch, 1983). Kyeong Won Yun shows that the aqueous extract from *A. campestris* ssp. *Caudate* hindered all vesicular and hyphal colonization except for the latter in *P. virgatum* (Kyeong Won Yun et al., 2007). *A. campestris* has also allelochemical properties by inhibiting the growth and the germination of some herbal species surrounding it (Neffati, 2000; Escudero et al., 2000).

This paper reports the first study of the effect of the harvest period on the chemical composition of the two *Artemisia* species essential oil: *A. herba-alba* and *A. Campestris* and their effect on fungi and bacterium yeasts.

Material and Methods

Plant material

Aerial parts of *A. Herba-alba* and *A. campestris* (Asteraceae) were collected randomly on May and December from Jabbes (12 Km from Maknessi in the Center of Tunisia) (Tab.I), Soil characteristics supporting the two studied species were shown in Tab.II. Samples were air-dried during 15 days in the laboratory at the room temperature.

200 g of sample was subjected to hydrodistillation for 3 h with 1000 ml of distilled water using a Clavenger apparatus. The oil obtained was separated from the distillate water and dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate.

Essential oil analyses

Gas chromatography (GC)

GC analysis was performed by HP 6890N GC system gas chromatograph fitted with a flame ionization detector (FID), using a HP Innowax column (60 m length, 0.25 mm id, 0.25 µm film thickness). The oven temperature held initially at 60 °C for 10 min after injection, then increased to 220 °C with 4°C/min heating ramp for 10 min and increased to 240 °C with 1 °C/min heating ramp then hold at this temperature for 10 minutes. Injector temperature was 250 °C; detector temperature was 250 °C; the carrier gas: nitrogen (1.0 ml/min); sample manually injected: 0.1 µl. The relative amount of components in the oil was calculated by electronic integration of FID peak areas and normalized without the use of response factor correction.

Gas chromatography/ Mass spectrometry (GC/MS)

GC/MS analysis was carried out using Shimadzu QP 5050A GC/MS with electron impact ionization (70 eV). A HP Innowax column (60 m, length, 0.25 mm id, 0.25 µm film thickness) was used. Oven Temperature Program: 60°C 10 min., 4 °C/min. 220°C 10 min., 1 °C/min. 240°C 10 min. The carrier gas was helium. mass range was 40-500 m/z. the column held initially at 60 °C for 10 min after injection, then increased to 220 °C with 4°C/min heating ramp for 10 min and increased to 240 °C with 1 °C/min heating ramp then hold at this temperature for 10 minutes.

Identification of the compounds

Compounds were identified by comparison of the chromatographic peaks retention times with those of authentic compounds analyzed under the same conditions, and by comparison of the retention indices (RI) (as Kovats indices) with literature data. The components of oil were identified by comparison of recorded mass spectra with those of a computer library (Wiley GC/MS Library).

Antioxidant activity, antibacterial and antifungal

Evaluation of antioxidant activity

DPPH radical trapping.

(I) Principle: The anti-radical activity was measured by degradation of DPPH: 2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl, which is a synthetic radical having an intense violet coloration. The electronic layer of this radical is saturated in contact with antioxidants, which explains the disappearance of her colour. This discoloration explains the power of the plant extract to trap this radical, which may be detected by a

spectrophotometer UV. It is therefore possible to detect the decrease in the intensity of this coloration by spectrophotometer. This discoloration highlights the antioxidant power of a sample by its ability to trap free radical.

(Ii) Measurement of the activity: The estimation of this anti-radical activity was measured by the method of Hanato et al. (1988). 1ml of extract at different concentrations is added to 250 μ l of a solution of DPPH (0.2 mM). After vigorous stirring, the mixture is kept for 30 minutes in the dark. Absorbance is measured at 517 nm using a UV-visible spectrophotometer, with reference to a control without extract. The anti-radical activity was estimated as percent inhibition using the following formula:

$$PI = (OD \text{ control} - OD \text{ sample} / OD \text{ control}) * 100$$

PI: percent inhibition.

Witnesses DO: absorbance of the negative control.

DO excerpt: absorbance of the extract solution.

The study of the variation of the antiradical activity depending on the concentration of the extracts is used to determine the concentration that corresponds to 50% inhibition (IC₅₀). A low value of the IC₅₀ corresponding to high efficiency of the extract.

Diffusion disks technique

The antibacterial activity was carried out in vitro against four strains of bacteria and 4 Candida strains. The antimicrobial activity of essential oils was tested using the disk diffusion method (28-30). In short, filter paper disks, 6 mm in diameter was impregnated with 10 μ l of diluted essential oils (HE 10 μ l / 90 μ l DMSO and 30 μ l and 70 μ l DMSO). The bacterial strains were inoculated (5 x 10⁵ cfu / ml) on HA (Oxoid) and the fungal strain was inoculated on Sabouraud dextrose agar (Oxoid), the whole was incubated for 24 h. Agar were distributed on sterile plates and sterile discs were impregnated with the oils and extracts (4 discs per plate, 9 cm in diameter). The plates were incubated at 37 ° C for 24 hours. After incubation, all the growth inhibition zones and zone diameters were measured in millimetres. DMSO, fluconazole and ketoconazole were used as positive controls (fig.1).

The determination of MIC and MBC

The minimum inhibitory concentration of essential oils was determined by agar dilution method according to the National Committee for guidelines for clinical laboratory NCCLS standards using a multipoint replicator and delivering 0.3 μ l of standardized microbial suspension. The final concentration of essential oils in the medium ranging from 1% to 0.0625% v / v. The plates were incubated at 37 ° C for 18-24 hours and the MIC was defined as the lowest concentration of essential oil to inhibit the visible growth. All determinations were performed in duplicate and control of growth medium consisting of MH.

Results and discussion

The yield is expressed by the volume of essential oil (by ml) obtained for the mass of 100 gr of dried plant material. The yield of the essential oils obtained from the air dried leaves of *A. campestris* harvested on December was 0.44 % and the one of May was 0.30 %. For *A. herba-alba* it was 0.5 % for air dried leaves harvested on December and 0.8 % for the one of May. The content of essential oil was more important for *A. herba-alba* than *A. campestris*. According to Ghanmi et al. (2010), the yields of essential oils for *A.*

herba-alba harvested on September, April and June were respectively about 0.56 %, 0.86 % and 1.23 %. Akrouit (2001) has found that the essential oil yield of *A. campestris* harvested on November is about 0.65 % for plants collected from four different regions on the south of Tunisia. However, the content obtained remains relatively small compared to the other species of *Artemisia*, such as *A. haussknechtii* (2.1% [ml/100g]) (Jalali et al., 2007) and *A. sieberi* (1.7% [ml/100 g]) (Ghasemi et al., 2006). This difference in performance can be explained by the nature of the species, the effect of the phenological stage of the plant and soil conditions of the region.

The chromatographic analysis of *A. campestris* essential oils showed fourteen and ten compounds respectively for the extracts of December (flower stage) and May (seed stage). For *A. herba alba* twelve compounds have been identified for both stages (table III). The composition of the essential oil of the two species differs depending on the harvest period. The essential oil of *A. campestris* was characterized by the presence of α -thujone (35.52 %) for the samples of December which was noted for the first time and it could explain the menthol odor of the plant for this stage. This compound was absent on the samples of May where the major compound was β -pinene (57.71 %). The presence and absence of some compounds depends on the phenological stages that's what Juteau et al. (2002) had noted for the essential oil composition of *A. campestris* var. *glutinosa* analyzed for different phenological stages and the results showed that monoterpenes were dominant compounds in the vegetative stage and aromatic compounds in the seed stage. The major compound in *A. herba-alba* essential oils was α -thujone in both samples of December and May with the percentage of 36.82 % and 43.00 % respectively followed by *cis*-sabinole (27.1-21.65 %) and lowest percentage of Chrysanthenyl acetate (6.50-4.97%). Paolini et al. (2010) had found a group characterized by a highest percentage of α -thujone (44.2-73.8 %), followed by lowest amounts of camphor (8.8-19.8%).

We find that essential oils have very low antioxidant activity. It is even unable to achieve a 50% inhibition with a very high concentration of 1500 μ g / ml of extract.

BHT is used as a positive control, it exhibits an IC₅₀ of about 12 μ g / ml. In general, we compare the results with this antioxidant and it is estimated that a particular extract has an interesting activity if it has an IC₅₀ close to that of BHT (less than 100 μ g / ml). Sometimes we do get lower IC₅₀ than 10 μ g / ml (table IV).

Given these results, it is not necessary to explore other antioxidants tests. Especially as in the other tests, starting concentrations should be high and amounts of essential oils will not allow to have several repetitions.

We noted a significant antifungal activity for different concentrations of essential oils used only. Weak antibacterial activity is noted for essential oils *A. campestris* collected in May against *B. cereus*.

The most significant antifungal activity is noted for essential oils of *A. campestris* in May against *C. krusei* and essential oil of *A. campestris* December against *C. albicans*. A lower antifungal activity is noted for essential oils of *A. herba-alba*. The antifungal activity appears for the 4 samples of oils for a concentration of 30 μ l (table V).

Our essential oils are effective against fungal strains and ineffective against Gram positive and gram negative strains in other research essential oils *A. campestris* and *A. herba-alba* has antibacterial and an important antifungal activity (Akrouit et al., 2010). The difference between the results is due to the fact that our oil was diluted with DMSO unlike those of Akrouit et al., Which have been used in raw form.

Our results reveal that the minimum inhibitory concentration does not vary depending on the period of extraction of essential oils for the two species (table VI). This prevents that essential oils of *A. campestris* possess improved antibacterial activity which is consistent with the results of the diffusion disc test.

The essential oils of two *Artemisia* species showed significant antifungal activity against a weak antimicrobial activity. This activity is not related to seasonal variability, but rather varies according to bacterial and fungal strains studied. By consequence, a very significant antioxidant activity was noted that decreases in any case the pharmacological importance of these oils which will be detailed in the following.

Our results had some similarities with those of Akrouit for both species since he found that the major compounds of *A. campestris* essential oil were α -pinene (45.8%) and β -pinene (12.5%) which is the case for the samples harvested on May and the major compounds for *A. herba-alba* oil were β -thujone (30.0%) and α -thujone (25.7%). The oil could be considered as thujone chemotype oil. It was reported on some other

studies this kind of oil for different samples in Tunisia (Haouari and Ferchichi, 2009; Akrou, 2004), Morocco (Julien Paolini et al., 2010 ; Lamiri et al., 1997 ; Ouyahya et al., 1990), Algeria (Boutekedjir et al., 1992, Vernin et al., 1994), Jordan (Hudaib and Aburjai, 2006).

Thujone has been found as major compound in other species of the genus *Artemisia* especially *A. absinthium*. (Lawrence, 1992) *Artemisia*'s essential oils composition had some similarities, it has been noted the presence of α -Pinene, β -Pinene, Camphene, Sabinene for samples from *A. absinthium*, *A. santolinifolia*, *A. vulgaris* and *A. campestris* (Khalilov et al., 2001).

Our results are in agreement with those of Mighri et al., (2010) which showed that the essential oil *A. herba-alba* from southern Tunisia (Medenine) has a very low antioxidant activity. Similar results were also observed for other *Artemisia* species such as *A. absinthium*, *A. biennis*, *A. cana*, *A. dracuncululus*, *A. frigida*, *A. longifolia* and *A. ludoviciana*, with a dominance of non-volatile compounds (Lopez Lutz. 2008). This low antioxidant activity was observed in the literature in oils types α -thujone, which is the case of oils of our two species *A. campestris* and *A. herba-alba* (Mighri et al., 2010. Lopez-Lutez et al., 2008).

Other research has found that four types of essential oils *A. herba-alba* have significant antifungal activity against all types of candida (Mighri et al., 2010).

Conclusion

Chemical variation of *A. herba-alba* essential oils showed a difference in the percentage of the compounds which is not the case for *A. campestris* essential oil since we had found absence of some compounds in relation with the phenological stage and the weather conditions. Further studies can explain more the biosynthetic pathway of the major compounds for the two species.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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Species	site	Longitude (N)	Latitude	(E) Elevation (m)
<i>A. herba-alba</i> <i>A. campestris</i>	Maknessi (Jabbes)	+34° 41' 12.03"	+9° 36' 19.03"	252

Figure 1: Disc diffusion test and the antifungal and antibacterial activity of the 4 essential oils extracts.

Table I: The collection site location of the two studied species of *Artemisia* and their geographic coordinates in Tunisia.

Table II. The two studied species of *Artemisia* supporting soil characteristics.

Soil characteristics	Jabbes
CLAY %	13
FINE LIMONS %	22
LIMONS COARSE %	1
FINE SAND %	45
COARSE SAND %	15
PH 1/2.5	7.6
SATURATION ml/100g	35
CONDUCTIVITY mmho/cm	2.7
LIMESTONE TOTAL %	9
ORGANIC MATTER %	0.1
CARBON %	0.1
P ₂ O ₅ ASSIM ppm (OLSEN)	12

Table III. Composition of the essential oils of *A. campestris* and *A. herba alba* related to the harvest period.

N°	RI	Components	<i>A. campestris</i> (%)		<i>A. herba alba</i> (%)	
			December	May	December	May
1	1032	α -pinene	1.10	5.51	0.24	0.31
2	1076	Camphene	1.41	0.40	0.10	0.13
3	1118	β -pinene	0.93	57.71	-	-
4	1132	Sabinene	0.35	3.40	0.11	0.14

5	1174	β -myrcene	-	2.80	-	-
6	1203	Limonene	0.83	6.53	-	-
7	1213	1,8-cineole	6.65	-	1.13	2.96
8	1218	β -phellandrene	-	1.16	-	-
9	1280	p-cymene	2.80	7.76	1.00	1.22
10	1312	3-octen-2-one	-	-	0.34	0.63
11	1430	α -thujone	35.52	-	36.82	43.00
12	1445	Filifolone	-	-	0.19	0.07
13	1451	β -thujone	5.92	-	10.73	11.53
14	1522	Chrysanthenone	-	-	0.48	1.47
15	1532	Camphor	11.04	-	-	-
16	1534	Chrysanthenyl acetate	-	-	6.50	4.97
17	1765	Geranyl acetate	0.96	-	-	-
18	1800	Cis-sabinol	13.33	-	27.01	21.65
19	2150	Spathulenol	2.01	4.10	-	-
20	2257	β -eudesmol	1.03	4.83	-	-
Total identified			83.88	94.2	84.65	88.08

RI: Relative retention indices calculated against n-alkanes (C9-C20) on the HP Innowax column.

Table IV: The inhibition percentage of production of the DPPH radical

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)			
E1	500	1000	1500
R1	0,31	0,264	0,256
R2	0,311	0,261	0,251
R3	0,309	0,262	0,25
MOY DO	0,31	0,26233333	0,25233333
%IP	7,46268657	21,6915423	24,6766169
IC50%	7,5	21,7	24,7

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)			
E2	500	1000	1500
R1	0,304	0,282	0,254
R2	0,3	0,28	0,258
R3	0,302	0,281	0,253
MOY DO	0,302	0,281	0,255
%IP	9,85074627	16,119403	23,880597
IC50%	9,9	16,1	23,9

Table V

Antibacterial activity of *A. campestris* and *A. herba-alba* against Gram+, Gram- and yeast strains

Inhibition diameter mm

Gram +	Essential oil μl						Antibiotics					
	E1 D		E1 M		E2 D		E2 M		M	VA	CN	CAZ
	10	30	10	30	10	30	10	30	5 μg	30 μg	10 μg	30 μg
<i>B. cereus</i> ATCC 11778	-	-	-	7 \pm 0.1	-	-	-	-	-	17 \pm	17 \pm	13 \pm
<i>S. aureus</i> NRLL B-767	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	22 \pm	19 \pm	17 \pm	24 \pm
Gram-												
<i>S.typhimirium</i> NRRL-B-4420	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	9 \pm	25 \pm	18 \pm

<i>E. coli</i> ATCC 25922	- -	- -	- -	- -	-	7±	20±	27±
Yeast strains								
<i>C. krusei</i> F6	- 7±	- 11 ±0	- 7 ±	- 8±	-	-	-	-
<i>C. albicans</i> ATCC 90028	7± 11±	8 ± 9 ±	7 ± 9±	- 7 ±	-	-	-	-
<i>C. tropicalis</i> y-12968	- -	- 7 ±	- -	- 7±	-	-	-	-
<i>C. glabrata</i> YB-181 (4.98)	- 2 ±	- 5 ±	- 3±	- 2±	-	-	-	-

-: No effect.

Table VI

<i>C. albicans</i> ATCC 90028	MIC	MBC
E1 D (µl/200µl) 30µl/170 µl	7,5	3,75
E1 M (µl/200µl) 15µl/185µl	7,5	3,75
E2 D (µl/200µl) 60µl/140µl	15	7,5
E2 M (µl/200µl) 60µl/140µl	15	7,5
F (µg/mL)	250	125
K (µg/mL)	250	125

MIC: Minimum inhibitory concentrations, MBC: Minimal bactericidal concentrations.